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“CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE: PRODUCTIVE OR COUNTER-PRODUCTIVE”

The term “civil” refers to the involvement and relations of citizens with one another or with the body politic or organized state (government), its divisions and departments, or to any shared space a citizen inhabit. To be civil means a citizen is part of something bigger like in a community, a society, a municipality, province or city, or a nation bound by a Constitution and respect. On the other hand, the term “disobedience” refers to the refusal to obey or negligence in obeying a demand or command like rules and laws. Disobedience is not a mindless defiance, it is a conscious choice and intentional. Being disobedient has consequences. Therefore, civil disobedience is the deliberate and public refusal to comply certain rules or laws as a peaceful form of political protest.

Citizens who practice civil disobedience accept willingly their punishment or the consequences of their act for breaking or not complying with certain rules or laws. In this way, the citizen, the civil disobedient, can demonstrate their deep concern with the situation they are protesting. The purpose of civil disobedience is to broadcast an unjust rule or law or a just cause; to appeal to the conscience of the public; to force negotiation with government officials; to “clog the machine” (in Henry David Thoreau’s phrase) with political prisoners, to get into court where one can challenge the constitutionality of a law – or some combination of these purposes.

Henry David Thoreau, an American author most famous for his essay *Civil Disobedience*, claimed that the individual is “a higher and independent power.” In other words, the citizens have the power to refuse to obey or comply with the rules or laws that they, the civil disobedients, consider unjust, that is to say, any individual that is part of an organized state or government, may stand apart from the rule or law which the organized state or government has implemented.

Civil disobedience can be productive in consideration of defending an individual’s rights. Examples of these are, first, the African-Americans who refused to obey or comply with the law that allowed them to sit only at the rear seats of the buses. Second, in the fight to stop abortions, many pro-lifers engage in non-violent actions by blocking the entrances to abortion clinics to prevent the deaths of the unborn babies. Third, the independence of India was largely the result of Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi’s program of Satyagra (Sanskrit for truth and firmness), which followed the principle of non-violent resistance to British colonial laws. Gandhi was able to use the technique as an effective political tool and play a key role in bringing about the British decision to end colonial rule of his homeland. Lastly, the First People Power Revolution in the Philippines. It is globally regarded as a landmark example of civil disobedience. It is a nonviolent defiance of unjust authority from the government. Public symbolic actions were present also during this time like boycotting businesses linked with former President Ferdinand E. Marcos and the presence of religious symbolisms. Acceptance of punishments or consequences were high during this protest or civil disobedience

as the civil disobedients risked being arrested, beaten violently, or killed. This civil disobedience by the Filipino people ended the dictatorship of then president Ferdinand E. Marcos.

Henry David Thoreau argued that sometimes the Constitution or the law is the problem and not the solution. A broad perspective of civil disobedience is seen as part for the struggle for justice-based-goals. This, as argued by Henry David Thoreau, makes civil disobedience productive in an unjust organized state or government.

On the other hand, the counter-productivity of civil disobedience can be argued in two grounds. First, civil disobedience is generally illegitimate. The fact that it is the deliberate refusal to obey or comply with the law, civil disobedience springs unlawful actions. Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi in 1930 called on Indian citizens to refuse to pay taxes, especially the tax on salt, to the British colonial government. Refusal to pay taxes to fund in building roads, bridges, and other public infrastructures is an example of civil disobedience and refusing to pay taxes decreases the quality of the nation. Second, the counter-productivity of civil disobedience is often inefficient because it distorts patterns of voluntary relationships, like the country's economy, business trading, among others, that make the life of the citizens better.

We can take into account the previous crisis in the Philippines with these two grounds of counter-productivity. The constant protests, rallies, and other civil disobedience activities brought the Philippines' status down in some other countries. Not only did the economy of the Philippines suffered and dropped down but also school days were cut short, which means, students gets less education whenever activities such as civil disobedience happens. Traffics are congested in affected areas and pollution are amongst its effect which, as we all know, causes risk to our health.

In view, the incompetence of the organized state or government programs is not sufficient justification for civil disobedience. If a government program is inefficient or cease to function, then one should be able to make this case to other citizens and get them to alter or abolish the program, exercising their civil rights according to bureaucratic processes. The costs of civil disobedience in terms of weakening the quality of the "goods" all seems to weigh more against the benefits of civil disobedience in fighting for merely inefficient policies. Counter-productivity to the society is heavy. Any act of civil disobedience weakens society and may lead to violence and anarchy. The scale seems to be in favor of civil disobedience when what government does to be injustice (justice-based). For example, racial indifference negates the liberty and equality to all people regardless of color, sex, age, or race among others. It is morally justifiable and productive to resist these actions of government. Civil disobedience has been an important and useful tactic in combating unjust governments and promoting freedom throughout the world. Efficient government, as agreed, should permit any illegitimate activities such as civil disobedience in order to harmonize or be in accord with the civil disobedient.